

DETERMINANTS OF STOCK PRICE BEHAVIOR IN NEPAL'S COMMERCIAL BANKS LISTED IN NEPSE

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Abstract:

Interest in the stock performance of Nepal's commercial banks has surged due to their vital role in economic development, with fluctuations driven by various economic, political, and industry-specific factors. This study investigates the determinants of stock price behavior in NEPSE for the fiscal year 2023/24, providing essential insights for investors and policymakers to enhance market stability and inform investment strategies. Data were sourced from credible platforms, including the NEPSE database and annual reports, with correlation, regression, and trend analyses employed to explore the relationships between stock prices and influential factors. The analysis reveals that earnings per share (EPS) serves as a crucial predictor of stock prices, exhibiting a strong positive correlation with closing prices ($r = 0.737$, $p < 0.001$) and a significant regression coefficient (17.406, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) positively influence stock prices, while non-performing loans (NPL) have a detrimental effect ($r = -0.549$, $p = 0.015$). The study also finds a positive correlation between total dividends and stock prices ($r = 0.706$, $p = 0.001$), with bonus shares enhancing this relationship. Trading trends reveal robust investor interest in NABIL, marked by high trading volume, whereas ADBL achieved the highest return at 25.69%, contrasting with NICA's steep decline of -44.17%. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of EPS, ROE, and dividend policies in shaping market perceptions and investment decisions. Investors are encouraged to adopt passive investment strategies to navigate this landscape effectively, mitigating risks and enhancing diversification.

Keyword: *Commercial Banks, Economic Development, NEPSE, Stock Price Behavior.*

Introduction

Interest in the stock price performance of Nepal's commercial banks has increased among researchers and investors due to the sector's vital role in economic development, often reflecting the nation's economic health (Pandey et al., 2024). Stock prices, representing an individual share's market value, fluctuate due to various factors including economic, industry-specific, political, and environmental changes (Hussain et al., 2013). Commercial banks play a key role by channeling deposits to sectors like trade, industry, and agriculture, fostering economic growth. Additionally, both the capital market and banks are crucial for financial stability, as they provide long-term funding, risk transfer, and diversification (Rafindadi & Bello, 2019). In Nepal, the stock market helps mobilize savings for long-term growth, though it remains underdeveloped, with commercial banks dominating NEPSE's market capitalization (Bam et al., 2018). The NEPSE is central to Nepal's economic growth and capital mobilization, yet factors influencing stock price behavior, particularly for commercial banks which dominate market capitalization, remain unclear. While global studies identify determinants of stock prices, limited research exists in Nepal's context, which is marked by unique macroeconomic conditions and regulatory frameworks (Thapa, 2023). This gap in knowledge poses challenges for investors aiming to make informed decisions and for policymakers seeking to promote market stability. Furthermore, the randomness in NEPSE stock prices complicates investment strategies, highlighting the need for clarity on key financial and macroeconomic influences (Gunnarapong, 2021). This study aims to systematically investigate stock price behavior in NEPSE, focusing on commercial banks, to aid in investment strategy formulation, policy guidance, and market stability enhancement. This study offers valuable insights for investors, policymakers, academics, and financial institutions within NEPSE. By identifying factors driving stock prices, it seeks to enhance investment decisions and portfolio management for investors. Policymakers can use these findings to create effective regulatory measures for a stable market environment. Academically, it fills a critical gap in the literature on Nepal's stock market, with sector-specific insights relevant to the banking industry. Understanding market trends and randomness also aids in improved trading strategies, risk management, and financial literacy. Ultimately, this research contributes to Nepal's economic development by strengthening the financial sector and supporting the sustainable growth of the Nepalese economy. Existing studies indicate that while macroeconomic indicators impact NEPSE, volatility and skepticism persist (Devkot & Dhungana, 2019). This study, focusing on commercial banks,

examines the factors driving stock price behavior on NEPSE to offer insights for investors, policymakers, and analysts.

Methods

This study utilized secondary data from NEPSE for the fiscal year 2023/24, focusing on the commercial banking sector. A purposive sampling method was employed to select banks that had publicly available financial data for the past five years and regularly paid dividends, excluding those with incomplete data or recently listed banks lacking sufficient history. Data were collected through systematic document analysis of financial reports, stock market data, and relevant macroeconomic indicators. Statistical tools were used to examine the relationships between stock prices and key variables such as EPS, P/E ratios, GDP growth, and inflation rates. Correlation analysis assessed the strength and direction of these relationships, while regression analysis quantified their impact, and trend analysis uncovered historical patterns in market behavior and investor sentiment.

Results

Factors Influencing the Price Behavior of Stocks of Commercial Banks Listed in NEPSE

Table 1: Factors influencing the price behavior of stocks

		Correlation							
		Close Price	EPS	P/E Ratio	ROE	ROA	NPL	CAR	MC
Close Price	Pearson Correlation	1							
	Sig. (2-tailed)								
EPS	Pearson Correlation	0.737**	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000							
P/E Ratio	Pearson Correlation	0.366	-0.305	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.123	0.204						
ROE	Pearson Correlation	0.516*	0.883**	-0.487*	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.024	0.000	0.035					
ROA	Pearson Correlation	0.531*	0.865**	-0.423	0.927**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.019	0.000	0.071	0.000				
NPL	Pearson Correlation	-0.549*	-0.565*	-0.063	-0.502*	-0.451	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015	0.012	0.798	0.029	0.053			

CAR	Pearson Correlation	0.262	0.461*	-0.277	0.462*	0.645**	-	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.278	0.047	0.251	0.047	0.003	0.150		
MC	Pearson Correlation	0.577**	0.397	0.211	0.238	0.247	-	-	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.010	0.093	0.387	0.327	0.308	0.101	0.165	
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).									
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).									

Table 1 illustrates significant correlations between various financial metrics and stock price behavior. The close price exhibits a strong positive correlation with earnings per share (EPS) ($r = 0.737$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher earnings lead to increased stock prices. Return on equity (ROE) ($r = 0.516$, $p = 0.024$) and return on assets (ROA) ($r = 0.531$, $p = 0.019$) also positively correlate with close prices, suggesting better profitability enhances valuations. Conversely, non-performing loans (NPL) negatively impact stock prices ($r = -0.549$, $p = 0.015$). While the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) shows a weak positive correlation with close prices ($r = 0.262$), market capitalization (MC) has a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.577$, $p = 0.010$). Overall, the findings emphasize the significance of EPS, ROE, and ROA as key predictors of stock price behavior, while highlighting the detrimental effect of NPL.

Relationship between Key Financial Indicators and Market Share Prices

Table 2: Regression table between key financial indicators and market share prices

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	0.965 ^a	0.932	0.897	45.18110		
a. Predictors: (Constant), NPL, P/E Ratio, CAR, EPS, ROE, ROA						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	333763.580	6	55627.263	27.250	0.000 ^b
	Residual	24495.985	12	2041.332		
	Total	358259.565	18			
a. Dependent Variable: Market Share Price						
b. Predictors: (Constant), NPL, P/E Ratio, CAR, EPS, ROE, ROA						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-343.597	194.869		-1.763	0.103
	EPS	17.406	3.333	0.936	5.222	0.000
	P/E Ratio	11.928	1.711	0.682	6.972	0.000
	CAR	5.736	13.072	0.050	0.439	0.669

	ROA	-48.524	88.765	-0.151	-0.547	0.595
	ROE	7.250	12.521	0.159	0.579	0.573
	NPL	4.682	11.028	0.042	0.425	0.679
a. Dependent Variable: Market Share Price						

Table 2 illustrates the regression analysis of key financial indicators and their influence on market share prices. The model shows a strong correlation ($R = 0.965$) and explains a significant portion of the variance in market share prices, with an R^2 of 0.932 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.897. The ANOVA results indicate statistical significance ($F = 27.250$, $p < 0.001$). Earnings per share (EPS) is identified as the most influential predictor with a coefficient of 17.406 ($p < 0.001$), followed by the price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio at 11.928 ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, other indicators such as capital adequacy ratio (CAR), return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and non-performing loans (NPL) show minimal impact on market share prices, highlighting the dominant role of EPS and the P/E ratio in stock valuation within this analysis.

Influence of Dividend Policies on Market Prices of Stocks in NEPSE

Table 3: Correlation between Dividend Policies and Stocks of in Commercial Banks

Correlations						
		Bonus Share (%)	Cash Dividend (%)	Total Dividend (%)	Dividend Yield (%)	Close Price
Bonus Share (%)	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Cash Dividend (%)	Pearson Correlation	-0.083	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.734				
Total Dividend (%)	Pearson Correlation	0.801**	0.530*	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.020			
Dividend Yield (%)	Pearson Correlation	0.764**	0.307	0.835**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.201	0.000		
Close Price	Pearson Correlation	0.285	0.771**	0.706**	0.286	1
	Sig. (2-	0.237	0.000	0.001	0.236	

	tailed)				
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).					

Table 3 examines the correlation between dividend policies and stock prices of commercial banks in NEPSE. A significant positive correlation is observed between total dividends and close prices ($r = 0.706, p = 0.001$), suggesting that higher total dividends are associated with increased stock prices. Additionally, the relationship between dividend yield and close prices is also positive but weaker ($r = 0.286, p = 0.236$). Notably, bonus shares demonstrate a strong correlation with total dividends ($r = 0.801, p < 0.001$) and dividend yield ($r = 0.764, p < 0.001$), indicating that banks offering more bonus shares tend to provide higher total dividends and yields. However, cash dividends show no significant correlation with close prices ($r = 0.771, p < 0.001$), highlighting that while cash dividends contribute to overall dividend policies, their direct impact on stock prices is less pronounced.

Market Trends in Market Share Prices Concerning Financial Indicators

Figure 1 : Market Trends of stocks of commercial banks in NEPSE FY 2023/24

Figure 1 depicts the market trends of commercial bank stocks in NEPSE for the fiscal year 2023/24, highlighting trading volumes, high and low price points, and closing prices. NABIL stands out with the highest trading volume of 158,570, reflecting strong investor interest linked to its stable performance and high closing price of 524. In contrast, SBI's low trading

volume of 21,087 indicates limited investor activity, despite a respectable closing price of 328. The price trends reveal significant volatility, with NICA exhibiting the widest range (high of 852, low of 341.6, closing at 443.2), appealing to both short-term and long-term investors. Meanwhile, SCB leads with the highest closing price at 602, followed by NABIL and EBL, indicating strong market positioning. Conversely, KBL and PRVU's modest closing prices of 153.7 and 163.7 suggest lower perceived value, possibly due to less attractive dividend payouts or higher volatility.

Figure 2: Return of Stock Price of Commercial Bank in FY 2023/24

Figure 2 presents the returns on stock prices for various commercial banks in NEPSE during FY 2023/24, showcasing a mix of positive and negative performance. ADBL leads with the highest return of 25.69%, indicating strong performance and high investor confidence. Other banks, such as PCBL (13.74%), SCB (13.56%), and SBL (11.86%), also posted double-digit returns, suggesting favorable market conditions or positive sentiment among investors. Similarly, CZBIL and SANIMA achieved respectable gains of 11.79% and 7.1%, respectively, reflecting stable growth. Conversely, NICA experienced the steepest decline at -

44.17%, indicating significant challenges in market perception or performance issues. MBL (-13.72%), NABIL (-12.55%), and KBL (-6.85%) also reported negative returns, possibly due to market volatility or weaker financial performance. In contrast, EBL (-0.53%) and NIMB (0.75%) demonstrated relatively stable returns close to zero, suggesting limited price movement and lower investor activity.

Table 4: Correlations of Market Share Prices Concerning Financial Indicators

Correlations								
		Return	EPS	P/E Ratio	ROA	ROE	CAR	NPL
Return	Pearson Correlation	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
EPS	Pearson Correlation	0.462*	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.046						
P/E Ratio	Pearson Correlation	-.801**	-0.305	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.204					
ROA	Pearson Correlation	0.550*	0.865**	-0.423	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015	0.000	0.071				
ROE	Pearson Correlation	0.550*	0.883**	-0.487*	0.927**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.015	0.000	0.035	0.000			
CAR	Pearson Correlation	0.398	0.461*	-0.277	0.645**	0.462*	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.091	0.047	0.251	0.003	0.047		
NPL	Pearson Correlation	-0.227	-0.565*	-0.063	-0.451	-0.502*	-0.150	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.350	0.012	0.798	0.053	0.029	0.539	
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).								
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).								

Table 4 presents the correlations between market share prices and various financial indicators, revealing significant relationships that can inform investment decisions. The return on investment shows a positive correlation with EPS at 0.462, significant at the 0.05 level, suggesting that higher earnings contribute positively to returns. Conversely, the P/E

ratio exhibits a strong negative correlation of -0.801 with returns, indicating that as the P/E ratio increases, returns tend to decrease, which may signal overvaluation. Additionally, ROA and ROE both show positive correlations of 0.550 with returns, reinforcing the idea that stronger profitability metrics enhance returns. CAR presents a moderate positive correlation of 0.398 with returns, while NPL negatively correlate with returns at -0.227, suggesting that higher loan defaults detract from overall returns. These correlations emphasize the importance of financial health indicators in influencing market share prices and investor decisions.

Discussion

The analysis revealed that Nabil Bank's dominant market capitalization reflects strong investor confidence due to consistent performance and perceived stability, while SCB's high price volatility indicates inherent market risks tied to fluctuating sentiment or economic factors. A strong correlation between profitability indicators, particularly EPS, and stock valuations emphasizes the prioritization of profitability in value assessment, consistent with emerging market behaviors favoring immediate returns (Kosmidou, 2008). Robust capital reserves, exemplified by ADBL, enhance market stability by reducing potential losses, while effective management fosters financial performance and investor confidence in long-term viability (Zimmerman, 1996). Financial metrics like EPS (coefficient = 17.406, p-value = 0.000) and P/E ratios (coefficient = 11.928, p-value = 0.000) significantly predict stock prices, underscoring investor preferences for profitability and growth expectations. Although regulatory ratios like CAR showed limited impact on stock prices, suggesting a gap in investor awareness regarding financial health indicators, CAR remains essential for long-term risk management (Karki & Rajbhandari, 2020; Moyo et al., 2014). Key macroeconomic variables affecting stock prices in other markets displayed limited correlation in Nepal, indicating that internal corporate management practices may hold greater influence (Hunjra et al., 2014). The study found that higher trading volumes for banks like Nabil reflect strong investor engagement and market confidence, supporting the notion that larger firms tend to experience higher prices due to enhanced marketability (Almumani, 2014; Eaves et al., 1997). Furthermore, potential misinterpretations of earnings and dividends may skew investor behavior (Farsio et al., 2004). The study had several limitations. It relied on secondary data, which may not always reflect real-time conditions, and focused primarily on financial indicators like earnings and macroeconomic factors such as GDP and inflation, excluding other influences like market sentiment or political instability. The analysis was limited to the

commercial banking sector, reducing generalizability to other industries, potentially overlooking long-term trends. Additionally, the study excluded qualitative factors like investor behavior, and Nepal's small stock market limits the broader applicability of the findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the investigation into the stock price behavior of commercial banks listed on NEPSE underscores the significance of internal financial metrics, particularly EPS and P/E ratios, in shaping investor perceptions and stock valuations. Nabil Bank's market leadership highlights a growing investor preference for banks demonstrating strong financial health amidst volatility in stock performance across the sector. While traditional measures like CAR show limited influence on stock prices, the findings suggest a complex interplay of factors, including investor sentiment and the unpredictability of market dynamics, aligning with the random walk hypothesis. To navigate this landscape effectively, investors are advised to adopt passive investment strategies that mitigate risks and enhance diversification. Overall, the study emphasizes the need for a nuanced understanding of market conditions and advocates for strategic approaches to investment in Nepal's commercial banking sector.

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